

MECHANICAL PERFORMANCE OF GLASS WOVEN FABRIC COMPOSITE: EFFECT OF HYBRID INTERPHASE WITH DIFFERENT SURFACE TREATMENT AGENTS

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1 Introduction

Combining with two or more components differing from physical and mechanical properties, composite materials can obtain a desirable characteristic. Fiber's surface morphology can be considered as one part of the nature properties of fiber/matrix bonding [1-2]. It is also generally recognized that bonding strength at the fibre-matrix interfaces has a great effects on composite material's mechanical properties, therefore, an appropriate engineered fiber/matrix interphase are able to improve composite's strength, toughness and environmental stability significantly [3]. As well know that, bonding strength was mainly depending on physical absorption, chemical reaction and bonding between fiber surface layer and matrix resin, which is strongly influenced by modification of fiber surface (surface treatment or sizing) [4-7]. The concept of "hybrid composites" is based on the composite principle which two or more materials are combined together to obtain better optimization of useful composite properties to suit specific requirements and applications than conventional composite, such as hybrid reinforcement and matrix hybridization. For further exploitation the idea of hybrid composites, current interest and attempt is performed to use the same type of fiber with different surface treatments for a given composite.

Up until now, glass reinforced polymer matrix composite material has already evolved to be a kind of important engineering material due to its light weight and excellent mechanical properties, which is also widely applied all around the world. There are many methods or treating agents for glass fiber's surface treatment including protecting fibers from damage and improving the adhesion between fiber and matrix. Played an important role in the field of glass fiber's surface treatment, silane coupling is

generally employed in industry for glass fiber' surface modification to improve both the abrasion between fibers and interfacial adhesion between delimited materials forming a functional interlayer by wet/chemical process.

As well known, silane coupling treated glass fiber is helpful for the interfacial bonding between fiber/matrix and total composite's mechanical property improvement, which is verified by a large amount of previous researches [8-10]. An analysis on intermittent bonding for high strength/high toughness composites were conducted by A. G. ATKINS, which demonstrated varying coating material' crucial effects in getting the desired effect and "toughness" of interfaces' important contribution [11]. Based on the so-called 'hybrid interface' concept, glass woven fabric composite laminates containing layers of low and high silane sizing concentrations were fabricated and investigated by Man-Lung Sham et.al, which reported hybrid layers composite obtained some improvements in tensile and bending strength compared with non-hybrid one with stable crack growth [12].

"Thick and Gradient Interphase" is always held and claimed by the author. That is to say, interphase phase is adhered around the fiber along with the thickness with varied mechanical property. So it seems the structure of interface/interphase is very complicated and important for applied composite material. Except silane coupling, other chemical sizing agents are also used as the surface treatment. PUD has been used as sizing for man-made fiber for a certain time. However, it is used mainly for the protection of fiber during fabrication. That is to say, PUD did not be considered popularly as surface treatment for fiber reinforced composites. Polyurethane is a kind of good surface coating

material, which is obtained increasing attention recently. In present research, in order to select the optimum interfacial conditions and properties between glass fiber reinforcement and thermosetting epoxy matrix in composite, three kinds of silane coupling agents containing with characterized function groups (epoxy- and amino-), isocyanate based polyurethane dispersion (PUD) solution with fixed pick-up ratio (6.49wt%) on glass fiber surface and their combination were applied as the surface treatments for heat cleaned glass woven fabric, the effects on composite's thermal characteristics and mechanical performance were also investigated and analyzed based on a serious of mechanical testing and fracture observation.

2 Materials and Fabrication

2.1 Materials

Thermosetting bisphenol-A epoxy (JER828) and amine-system harder (JER-W) were used as the matrix system in a ratio of 100:24, supplied by Mistubishi Chemistry.LTD. Finishing agent on the glass-cloth was wiped out through heat clean method also by the company, which was so called non-treat (heat clean) glass-cloth performed as reinforcement.

Polyurethane dispersion (Grade UW-5002), amino- (KBM 603, N-2-(aminoethyl)-3-aminopropyl trimethoxysilane) and epoxy- (KBM 403, 3-Glycidoxypropyltrimethoxy trimethoxysilane; KBE 403, 3-Glycidoxypropyltrimethoxy triethoxysilane) types of silane coupling agent are obtained from UBE Industries Ltd. and Shin-Etsu chemical company in Japan.

PU surface treatment applied in this study was an expanding chain mainly composed of two parts: urea link and hydrophilic group. KBM403 and KBE403 are a kind of silane sizing containing with epoxy-function group, which can perform as the same with normal organic epoxy- function to conduct a chemical reaction with alcohol and other water acid base, especially suitable for chemical bonding with a polymer including amino- function. On the contrary, KBM603 attributed to a silane coupling with amino-function, which basically reacted with acid, ester, ketone, epoxy and halogen compounds.

2.2 Composites' Fabrication

None-treat and treated glass woven fabrics reinforced thermosetting epoxy were fabricated by hot press molding method. Firstly, mixed epoxy and harder were put into the vacuum oven for 15-20 minutes at 70°C in order to increase the liquidity for better mixing and getting rid of the entrapped air-bubble. Afterwards, one layer of treated or non-treat fabric with the size of 250 mm × 250 mm was impregnated into matrix resin within 2-3 minutes to keep the matrix resin ' s fluidity. Impregnated composite sheets were cured by hot press machine with applied force of 170 Newton. After being initially cured at 100°C for 2 hours, molded panels were post-cured at 175°C for 4 hours.

2.3 Surface treating process

Prior to molding, the weight of pre-cut heat clean glass clothes was measured as M_0 . For the case of solo treatment, pre-cut fibre cloth were submerged into 0.5wt% concentration of conditioned silane solution with 0.2mol/L acetic acid and PUD original solution respectively for 1 minute. Clean tissue was used to wipe out the redundant solution on treated glass-cloth surface after taking out from the bath. Subsequently, the PUD and silane coupling treated glass-clothes were put in convection oven for solvent ' s evaporation for 1 hour at 140°C and 20 minutes at 90°C respectively. While for the case of hybrid one, glass cloth was treated by silane coating firstly followed by PU treating process. Finally, the weight of treated glass-cloth M_p was measured again for reference. Evaluation equation for treatment agent's pick- up ratio (P%) at unit glass-cloth weight was defined as Eq.1

$$P\% = (M_p - M_0) / M_0 * 100 \quad (1)$$

Where M_p corresponded to treated-weight of glass-cloth after drying in oven, M_0 corresponded to non-treat weight or silane treated weight. Because the silane coupling layer surrounding glass fiber was too thin to measure the weight in current study, so P% existed in this paper stands for the PU' pick-up ratio.

3 Experiments

3.1 Observation by optical microscope

Both cross-section and fiber bundle of fabricated virgin and treated GFRP were observed by a Reflection-Type Optical Microscope. Selected specimens were embedded with epoxy resin following by 12 hours' resin cure in room temperature and then polished by a polishing machine (Doctor-Lab, ML-180) before observation.

3.2 Treatment layer thickness calculation

On basis of the cross-section's photographs for both virgin and treated GFRP taken under 2500 magnification, every 20 points of single glass fiber bundles from random 5 strands (Total 100 points) were selected. Employing with Image-J analysis software, every type of bundle's nominal diameter values were scientific measured following by real size's transforming on basis of reference scale.

3.3 Tensile Test

Tensile test was performed using an Instron Universal Testing Machine at a constant crosshead speed of 1 mm/min. For each type, 5 pieces of samples with the geometry of 200 mm X 25 mm (length X width) was repeated.

3.4 Dynamic Mechanical Analysis

Prepared samples with 6 mm X 30 mm (width X length) were tested and analyzed by DMA using TA instruments Co., Ltd., DMA 2980. Testing temperature was controlled from 40°C to 250 °C with the heating rate of 3°C/min. 3 pieces of each kind composite were repeated with 0.1 newton of static force.

3.5 Scanning Electron Microscope

The fracture surfaces after tensile test were inspected by a field emission scanning electron microscope (Hitachi, S-4200) (SEM) with a focus on fiber pull-out performance, fiber/matrix interfacial

interactions and fracture morphologies to characterize interfacial bonding/cohesion and their relationships to the test results. Gold was sputtered onto the specimens for electron conductivity before SEM observation.

4. Results and Conclusions

4.1 Resin impregnation condition and interfacial properties

Resin impregnation condition and the interfacial interaction between fiber/matrix after treating are summarized in Fig.1. It's clearly to note that cross-section of solo silane treated composite became smoother and flatter with decreased un-impregnated hollow holes comparing with virgin GFRP, which clarified the good interfacial adhesion and bonding between fiber and matrix. On the other hand, solo PU treated composite showed decreased holes and redundant PU polymer attached around fiber bundles. In particular, a combined effect of hybrid interphase was displayed. In a word, resin impregnation property was greatly improved by silane sizing, PUD treatment and their hybrid interphase coating on glass fiber.

Fig.1 Expanded glass fiber strand optical observation of virgin and treated composites

4.2 Treatment layer thickness comparison

All different treatment layer's thickness were calculated and summarized in Tab.1, various silane

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coupling treatment layers had nearly the same coating thickness around glass fiber bundle with 0.16 μ m. However, PUD layer's thickness attached around held the largest than other solo treatments.

According to the Figure.2, it is worthwhile to note the sharp differences among hybrid interphase themselves and the comparison with solo treatment. As the chemical structure and its reaction mechanism of KBM403, KBE403, KBM 603 and PUD treatments mentioned ahead, silane layer can be considered to be an important bridge between virgin glass fiber and PUD treatment contained in hybrid interphase, whose inorganic part bonded with glass fiber surface and organic function group participated in chemical reaction with PU layer. Therefore, it is clearly to found the pronounced thickness increment after combining PUD for KBM 403 and KBE 403 owing to their internal chemical bonding. In the contrast, only a little PUD's physical absorption and fixation existed after combining PUD for KBM603. Consequently, it was deserved to demonstrate a positive correlation between the chemical reaction among hybrid interphase and its coating thickness.

Type	Real Diameter (um)	Treatment Thickness um
Virgin	8.89	0
KBM403/GF/Epoxy	9.18	0.145
KBE403/GF/Epoxy	9.21	0.16
KBM603/GF/Epoxy	9.24	0.175
PUD/GF/Epoxy	9.44	0.275
KBM403+PUD/GF/Epoxy	9.4	0.255
KBE403+PUD/GF/Epoxy	9.5	0.305
KBM603+PUD/GF/Epoxy	9.28	0.195

Tab.1 Various treatment layers' thickness summary

Figure.2 Treatment thickness comparison between solo and hybrid interphase

4.3 Tensile Property

Typical tensile stress-strain (S-S) plotting curves of virgin, solo treated and hybrid interphase composites were gathered and illustrated in the Fig.3 a & b. It was clearly to found that after various solo silane and PUD sizing for virgin glass fiber woven fabric, not only the strength but also the elongation at break has gained greater improvement to different extent respectively. Especially for the KBM603 (amino-) silane treated one, treated composite performed the most pronounced improvement in strain, which can be owed to the good cohesive property through organic function's chemical reaction with matrix resin.

Unlike the solo silane treated composites, the composite with additional PUD as hybrid interphase show the similar tensile stress-strain curves. All of the composites after combined treatment of silane and PUD represented nearly the same strength and strain, which were also approaching to solo PUD treatment's improving results. According to this phenomenon, it seems to show that the PU has amendatory effect not only for glass fiber but also glass fiber with silane coating.

Figure.3 Typical S-S curves among virgin, various silane coupling and PUD treated GFRP

According to Fig. 4 & 5, two clear histogram figures were illustrated for both tensile modulus and strength comparison among virgin and various sizing treated composites. Referring to the tensile modulus, excepting with individual improvement in silane treated group, both PUD and hybrid interphase treated composites displayed a decreasing trend compared with virgin GFRP. Especially, composite's modulus performed more serious descending after hybrid treating, which was considered to be thicker and more flexible interphase region existed between glass fiber and matrix resin.

However, it's worthwhile to note that tensile strength showed desired improvement effect after any kind of surface treating process. In sharp contrast with composite's tensile modulus descending trend after latter PUD surface treatment in hybrid interphase, their tensile strength obtained a further improvement with varying degrees. Consequently, total enhanced effect of composite's tensile strength was depended on latter surface treatment (PUD)'s bonding with both matrix resin (epoxy) and former treatment (silane).

Figure.4 Tensile modulus comparison among virgin and various treated GFRP

Figure.5 Tensile strength comparison among virgin and various treated GFRP

4.4 SEM observation of post failure samples

Samples' fracture surfaces after tensile test were shown in Fig.6 & 7. Special concentration was placed on 0°direction (loading-bearing) fibers' pulling out performance and fiber characterized morphology.

Comparing with the pulling-out fiber morphology feature in virgin GFRP, treated ones all represented rougher fiber surfaces and matrix resin's adhesion around bundles, which can be determined as the strong interphase bonding. Various solo silane sizing, PUD treatment and their hybrid interphase were applied to promote physical absorption, chemical bonding and interfacial cohesion between fiber/matrix which in turn contributed the rise to high tensile strength. By contrast with solo silane treated composites, the one with hybrid interphase containing PUD treatment showed longer pulling-out fiber and comparable uniform failure mode rather than extensive fiber pull-out occurrence in the view of a random fiber strand, which can be presumed to be homogeneous efficient stress transfer through enough interphase region provided by hybrid treatment process.

Figure.6 Pulling-out fiber's morphology comparison among virgin, silane, PUD and silane/PUD hybrid treated composites

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Figure.7 Fiber pulling-out performances comparison between solo silane and hybrid treated composites in random strand

4.5 Dynamic Mechanical Analysis (DMA) of composites

Typical storage modulus and Tan δ value results during DMA testing were plotted in Fig.8 & 9.

As shown in Fig.8 (a), compared with virgin glass/epoxy composite, both solo silane sizing and PUD treated composites manifested a pronounced decrement in initial storage modulus E' . In general, with increasing test temperature, silane treated composite displayed a relative gentle decreasing after sustaining the initial storage modulus for a long testing period. On the contrary, PUD coated composite exhibited a continuous descending trend from the beginning. Regarding virgin GFRP as referenced standard, descending stage from solid to rubbery state showed an expand area and shifting toward lower temperature for PUD treated case, while silane treated group showed the reverse behaviors. In a word, PUD layer's flexibility characteristic and silane treatment's improved effect on composites' viscoelasticity and thermotolerance performance were distinguished and indicated.

Referring to the storage modulus change behavior of composites containing with hybrid interphase (Fig.8

b), a neutralized effect between solo PUD and silane sizing phenomenon was detected. Even if the descending area was still broad, yet decreasing trend became more gentle than solo PUD treated one following by a period of comparable stable initial storage modulus.

Composite sample's Tan Delta values recorded during the range of testing temperature were collected and plotted into Fig.9 a & b as following. The specific temperature corresponded to Tan Delta peak existence was nearly the same (around 190°C) between virgin GF/Epoxy and silane treated groups. However, PUD treated one appeared one more Tan Delta peak at lower temperature (140°C), nearby which Tan Delta peaks were also found in all silane/PUD hybrid treated composites correspondingly. Additionally, one more slight Tan Delta peak emerged at 210°C for all hybrid treated composites, which was deemed as by-product's peak.

Only taking the Tan Delta peak value at 190°C for comparison, it was clearly to find hybrid treated composites manifested the smallest value (around 0.0) than solo treatment (around 0.08) and virgin one (0.13). In other words, decreased Tan Delta peak value by adding surface treatment especially hybrid one means improved/higher tensile strength stored before entering rubbery state according to Tan Delta peak value's defined meaning, which also agreed well with real static tensile test.

Figure.8 (a) Storage modulus summary among virgin and solo treated composites

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Figure.8 (b) Storage modulus summary among virgin and hybrid treated composites

Figure.9 (a) Tan Delta value versus testing temperature among virgin and solo treated composites

Figure.9 (b) Tan Delta value versus testing temperature among virgin and hybrid treated composites

Conclusion

In order to make sure of stress efficient transfer between fiber/matrix interphase, fiber surface treatment or optimization and matrix's chemical modification are usually applied. As well known, microstructure of fiber surface can obtain significant alternation through various surface treatment/sizing, which also result in composite's different interphase properties and "boundary effect". In current study, thermosetting epoxy resin and heat cleaned glass woven fabric modified by solo polyurethane dispersion (PUD), various silane coupling solutions with 0.5wt% concentration and their combined hybrid treatment were performed as matrix and reinforcement respectively. Special emphasis was placed on distinct interfacial characteristics of various solo surface treatments for glass fiber and beneficial effect after hybrid treating process.

With respect to fiber surface modification, every treatment layer's thickness coated on the glass fiber was measured correspondingly. Simultaneously, treated composites' fiber-impregnation condition was discussed and compared with virgin one. In addition, mechanical properties of virgin and treated composites in tension were investigated following by their fracture surfaces' examination with scanning electron microscope. To establish a correlation between static and dynamic mechanical properties and thermal performance study, a cooperative analysis of DMA on molecular mobility of matrix and interfacial adhesion property was carried out. Consequently, it was demonstrated that:

1. Resin impregnation property was greatly improved with decreasing un-impregnated areas after silane sizing, PUD solution and their hybrid interphase coating on glass fiber.
2. In contrast with solo silane treated composite, final coating thickness of corresponded hybrid one was depended on chemical bonding between hybrid interphase.
3. Comparing with virgin GFRP, solo PUD, silane and hybrid treated composites all displayed a desirable tensile strength and strain improvement. It is worthwhile to indicate that

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total enhanced effect of hybrid treated composite's tensile strength was consisted of latter surface treatment (PUD) 's bonding with both matrix resin (epoxy) and former treatment (silane).

4. Comparing with the pulling-out fiber morphology feature in virgin GFRP, treated ones all represented rougher fiber surfaces and matrix resin's adhesion around bundles, which can be determined as the strong interphase bonding and contribute a rise for strength in turn.
5. Based on measured viscoelasticity characteristic by DMA, compared with virgin glass/epoxy composite, both solo silane sizing and PUD treated composites manifested a pronounced decrement in initial storage modulus E' . Furthermore, PUD layer's flexibility characteristic and silane treatment's improved effect on composites' viscoelasticity and thermotolerance performance were indicated by the range and shift direction of descending stage from solid to rubbery.

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